

Researchers in Ukraine: Output, international collaboration, impact, heritage and sex, 1995 to 2021

Grant Lewison¹, Philip Roe², Richard Webber³, Valentina Markusova⁴, Richard Sullivan⁵

¹grantlewis@aol.co.uk, ⁵richard.sullivan@kcl.ac.uk

King's College London, Department of Cancer Policy, Guy's Hospital, Great Maze Pond, London, SE1 9RT (UK)

²philip@evaluametrics.co.uk

Evaluametrics Ltd, 157 Verulam Road, St Albans, AL3 4DW (UK)

³richardwebber@originsinfo.com

OriginsInfo Ltd, 3 Bisham Gardens, London, N6 6DJ (UK)

⁴valentina.markusova@gmail.com

Stamford, CT 06902 (USA)

Abstract

The invasion of Ukraine by the Russian army in February 2022 caused us to look back at Ukrainian science before the war and appraise its strengths and weaknesses, so that after peace and reconstruction it may flourish again and be better attuned to the new era. We examined its publications recorded in the Web of Science (WoS) from 1995 to 2021, and evaluated their quantity and impact, their major fields and Ukraine's international partners. We also looked at the outputs of the 26 individual *oblasts* or regions, and the heritage of the researchers in each, Ukrainian or Russian, based on their surnames and given names. Ukrainian scientific output, at about 0.5% of that of the world, was high relative to its wealth, but its impact was rather low, probably because of a lack of contestable funding. It was skewed towards the physical sciences and away from biology and medicine, and so may have led to poorer health in Ukraine than in its geographical neighbours. Its researchers were more likely to be of Ukrainian than Russian heritage the further west they were located. Women were well represented in Ukrainian science and formed more than half the total in most *oblasts*.

Introduction

The invasion of Ukraine, a sovereign state and a Founding Member of the United Nations since its inception in 1945, by the forces of the Russian Federation (henceforward simply Russia) on 24 February 2022 has been a major focus of world attention. However, Russian territorial aggression pre-dates this with its support for the Separatists in the eastern Donbas region from March 2014 onwards, and its invasion and annexation of Crimea, also in 2014. The latter was not recognized internationally, and the territorial integrity of the country was confirmed by a vote of the United Nations on 27 March 2014. Ukraine has had a long association with Russia because for over 70 years it was an integral part of the Soviet Union, although under the constitutions of both countries it had a theoretical right to secede, which was exercised in 1991.

Although it has a language that has many similarities with Russian, including the use of the Cyrillic script, Ukraine has a distinct culture and identity. This has been particularly evident, from a political standpoint, since the “Revolution of Dignity” (Революція гідності) or Maidan revolution, of 2013-14, which led to the removal of President Viktor Yanukovich and the subsequent election of Presidents Pedro Poroshenko in 2014, and Volodymyr Zelenskyi in 2019. Since 2014 there has been a major effort by the Ukrainian government to emphasise the cultural differences between Ukraine and Russia, with support for the teaching of Ukrainian as the primary language (Friedman, 2010). Nevertheless, many Ukrainians have relatives in Russia, have (or had) close friendships with Russians, and indeed continue to speak this language, and find the new language restrictions unpleasant (Nedozhogina, 2021).

How these socio-political changes have impacted the situation with Ukrainian research is not well documented. Ukraine has a long history of research and development. The National Academy of Science of Ukraine (NAS) was one of the main basic research institutions and was founded in 1919. Two founders of the NAS were Professor Volodymyr Ivanovych Vernadsky, who was a Russian, Ukrainian and Soviet mineralogist, and Hetman Pavlo Skoropadskyi. The latter was for a short time the head of Ukraine when it became an independent state after the revolution in Russia in 1917 (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pavlo_Skoropadskyi).

Ukraine is classified by the World Bank as a “lower-middle” income country, and in 2018, its income *per caput* was about 30% of that in Russia, and its gross domestic product (GDP) was barely 8% of that of Russia, and 0.15% of the world. Nevertheless, its research output in 2016-20 (articles and reviews recorded in the Web of Science, WoS © Clarivate Analytics) was about 16% of that of Russia, and about 0.5% of the world, so it was performing very well relative to its GDP. However, its research portfolio was very skewed towards some major scientific fields, see Figure 1, with a continuing heavy focus on traditional strengths of physics and mathematics, almost certainly a Soviet legacy. There was a relative paucity of medical, information science, and agricultural research, perhaps surprisingly, given that agriculture accounted for 10% of its economy in 2021, and over 40% of its exports.

Figure 1. The distribution of the Ukraine research portfolio between 2016 and 2020, by major scientific field compared with that of the world (articles + reviews in the Web of Science). *AGRI* = agriculture; *BIOL* = biology, *CHEM* = chemistry, *ENGR* = engineering, *GEOG* = geography, *HUMA* = humanities, *INFO* = information sciences, *MATE* = materials sciences, *MATH* = mathematics, *MEDI* = medicine, *MULT* = multidisciplinary sciences, *PHYS* = physics, *SOCI* = social sciences.

In this paper, we sought to determine the main characteristics of Ukrainian research publications, and the pattern of international collaboration. We selected a study period of 27 years for this, from 1995 to 2021. For the last two years (2020-21), we also examined the propensity of the Ukrainians to collaborate with researchers from six country groups in some 12 major fields. For this analysis, we used fractional counts of countries, based on the institutional addresses on each paper, but for the main time series we used integer counts of papers, taken directly from the WoS.

For the most recent period, 2020-21, we also investigated who the researchers were, and in particular whether they could be considered to be of a Russian or Ukrainian background or heritage. This is possible to some extent because there are differences between many of the researchers’ names, both surnames and given names, in their origins and in the way that they

are spelt and transliterated into the Roman alphabet. For example, Balatskiy (Балацкий) is Russian and Balitskii (Балицкий) or Balyts'kyi (Бальцкий) are Ukrainian. However, this is changing, as Ukraine has been altering the format of the names of people of Russian heritage in an attempt to make them more Ukrainian, despite resistance from some quarters (Knoblock, 2019).

There is a long tradition of the examination of Ukrainian names, and their formation (Vyrsta & Rokitska, 2020), as there is in other countries. In particular, suffixes played an important role in their creation (Vyrsta, 2021), and some of them are particular to Ukraine rather than to Russia, such as *chuk*, *iuk* and *skyi* (the latter sometimes transcribed as *skii*).

Ukraine has a complicated history, and over the centuries its population has included, as well as Russians, many people from lands in central and eastern Europe which at some time have formed part of Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, and Slovakia, all of which border Ukraine. Administratively, it is divided into 26 regions, or *oblasts*, including the capital Kyiv and its surrounding area, see Table 1. The *oblasts* in the east, notably Donetsk and Luhansk, tend to have higher proportions of people of Russian heritage than those in the west, particularly Lviv and Volyn. As a consequence of the Russian invasions in 2014 and 2022, there has been a large-scale exodus of refugees from the east both to the western *oblasts* and to countries in the European Union (EU) and beyond, such as the United Kingdom (UK). There has also been a movement of people into and out of Crimea. However, research is concentrated in Kyiv, the capital, which has gained population, as has its surrounding region. We examined research outputs from the individual *oblasts* over the long study period of 1995 to 2021 in order to see how this had changed over the 27 years.

We then sought to determine the balance of the sexes in Ukrainian research in the different *oblasts*, and how it has changed over time. Female researchers have traditionally suffered from both overt and covert discrimination, and still do so, despite many studies showing (and bewailing) this (Hoke, 1993; O'Brien, 1997; Ledin et al., 2007; Danell & Hjerm, 2013; Wagner et al., 2017). A recent study on cancer research (Lewison et al., 2022) suggested that the best-performing countries were those in Scandinavia, some Hispanic and Lusophone countries in Europe and Latin America, and countries in eastern Europe that continued to provide good and inexpensive child-care. Ukraine had increased the presence of female cancer researchers from 29% in 2009 to 43% in 2019, a major improvement, and one that was much greater than the world average.

Our intention in this paper is to show the strengths and weaknesses of Ukrainian science before the full-scale war so that they may be addressed after the war is over. Ukrainian research is continuing despite the hostilities (Arado, 2022; Arbuzova, 2023), but it is hard to make plans at present.

Table 1. List of the 26 *oblasts* in Ukraine with their populations in 2012 and 2021 (thousands), the percentage change, the estimated number of researchers in 2020-21, and the percentage of the population who were researchers. *Oblasts* ranked by this percentage.

<i>Oblast</i>	<i>Code</i>	<i>Pop 2012</i>	<i>Pop 2021</i>	<i>% change</i>	<i>Researchers</i>	<i>%</i>
Kyiv city	KYV	2901	2962	2.1	14040	0.474
Kirovohrad	KIR	975	920	-5.6	2783	0.302
Kharkiv	KHA	2720	2634	-3.2	5656	0.215
Lviv	LVV	2535	2498	-1.5	3781	0.151

Sumy	SUM	1115	1053	-5.5	1092	0.104
Chernivtsi	CNI	910	897	-1.5	815	0.091
Odesa	ODE	2387	2368	-0.8	2053	0.087
Chernihiv	CNV	1047	977	-6.7	776	0.079
Dnipropetrovsk	DNI	3259	3142	-3.6	2215	0.070
Zaporizhzhia	ZAP	1756	1667	-5.1	1148	0.069
Ternopil	TER	1067	1031	-3.4	709	0.069
Ivano-Frankivsk	IVF	1383	1361	-1.6	898	0.066
Vinnitsia	VNN	1604	1529	-4.7	950	0.062
Poltava	POL	1441	1372	-4.8	841	0.061
Volyn	VOL	1043	1027	-1.5	501	0.049
Cherkasy	CKY	1246	1178	-5.4	529	0.045
Zhytomyr	ZHY	1249	1195	-4.3	499	0.042
Zakarpattia	ZAK	1259	1250	-0.7	503	0.040
Kherson	KHE	1064	1017	-4.4	394	0.039
Mykolaiv	MKV	1160	1108	-4.4	395	0.036
Rivne	RIV	1162	1148	-1.2	397	0.035
Khmelnytskyi	KHM	1296	1244	-4.0	341	0.027
Kyiv region	KYM	1732	1789	3.3	414	0.023
Donetsk	DON	4388	4100	-6.6	776	0.019
Luhansk	LUH	2264	2121	-6.3	324	0.015
Crimea	CRI	1964	2417	23.1	218	0.009

Methodology

Our study of the research output of Ukraine in 1995-2021, before the Russian invasion of February 2022, covered articles and reviews in the WoS in all fields of science. We interrogated the “Core Collection” and used all six of the databases, including the Emerging Sciences Citation Index, which was added in 2015, and covers many Ukrainian (and Russian) journals. [However, the two sets of Conference Proceedings did not contain any of these two document types.] We compared the volume of Ukrainian publications with that of the world, and examined the amount of international collaboration. We combined the other countries into six major groups in order to simplify the analysis:

- Western Europe (the first 15 Member States of the European Union, plus Iceland, Norway and Switzerland) – EUR18;
- Eastern Europe (the last 13 Member States to join the European Union, including Cyprus and Malta) – E EUR;
- The other Former members of the Soviet Union, plus Bosnia & Hercegovina, Kosovo, North Macedonia and Serbia – FSU;
- Other countries in Asia, including China and India – Asia;
- Canada and the USA – CA + US; and
- The Rest of the World – RoW.

For the analysis of international collaboration, the countries in the first four groups listed above were the ones tabulated in Table 2.

Table 2. Four groups of countries with which Ukrainian researchers may have collaborated.

<i>Western Europe</i>	<i>Eastern Europe</i>	<i>Former Soviet Union</i>	<i>Asia</i>	
Austria	Bulgaria	Albania	Afghanistan	Myanmar
Belgium	Croatia	Armenia	Bahrain	Nepal
Denmark	Cyprus	Azerbaijan	Bangladesh	North Korea
Finland	Czech Republic	Belarus	Bhutan	Oman
France	Estonia	Bosnia & Hercegovina	Brunei	Pakistan
Germany	Hungary	Georgia	Cambodia	Palestine
Greece	Latvia	Kazakhstan	China	Papua N. Guinea
Iceland	Lithuania	Kirgizstan	India	Philippines
Ireland	Malta	Kosovo	Indonesia	Qatar
Italy	Poland	Moldova	Iran	South Korea
Luxembourg	Romania	North Macedonia	Iraq	Saudi Arabia
Netherlands	Slovakia	Russian Federation	Israel	Seychelles
Norway	Slovenia	Serbia	Japan	Singapore
Portugal		Tajikistan	Jordan	Sri Lanka
Spain		Turkmenistan	Kuwait	Syria
Sweden		Uzbekistan	Laos	Taiwan
Switzerland			Lebanon	Thailand
United Kingdom			Malaysia	Timor Leste
			Maldives	Turkey
			Mongolia	

We sought to determine the impact of the Ukrainian research papers in comparison with those of its seven neighbouring countries: Belarus, Hungary, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Russia, and Slovakia. We counted citations to papers from each of five years, 2013-17, in the publication year and four subsequent years, called ACI for Actual Citation Impact. For most of the countries, but not Poland or Russia, the numbers of papers in each year were fewer than 10,000 so that the numbers of citations were displayed in the WoS and could easily be copied and pasted to a spreadsheet. For these two countries, their papers were divided into smaller groups based on the initial letters of the journals in which they were published. For Poland, four groups sufficed, but for Russia, with over 208,000 papers in the five years, we needed to divide them into seven groups.

We determined the research outputs of the individual *oblasts*, as integer counts, directly from the WoS by means of geographical filters based on the names of all the cities within each (plus the name of the *oblast* if it was not also the name of a city). [There are 461 cities and their locations were taken from this source: List of cities in Ukraine – Wikipedia: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_cities_in_Ukraine.] For each *oblast*, we also determined

the number of reviews, a simple measure of the esteem in which their researchers were held by journal editors (Lewison, 2009), as a percentage of the total output, and the ratio of outputs between 2017-21 and 1995-99.

However, we found that the sum of the outputs of the individual *oblasts* was less than the total Ukrainian output. [It should, of course, be larger because of inter-*oblast* collaboration.] The cause was the variation in the way the names of Ukrainian cities (and some *oblasts*) were transcribed from the Ukrainian alphabet into the Roman one. For example, Kyiv, the capital city, was often written as Kiev, particularly in earlier years when Russian spelling (and pronunciation) were common. We therefore searched all the Ukrainian addresses on papers from 2020-21 (see below) and also from 1995-99, and matched the names of their cities to the individual *oblasts*. Although many names matched those in the list that we had downloaded from Wikipedia, some did not, but we could do this manually as the spellings were clearly similar. Some other cities not on the list were matched to an *oblast* by reference to information on the world-wide web. We were then able to add additional search terms to the 26 geographical search statements that we used to identify papers from each *oblast*.

This added many papers to the tally, which increased from a total of 72,869 to 162,605, or from 49% of the Ukrainian total to 110%. However, this was clearly still an incomplete tally as it was less than 100% for the 14 years, 1995-2008. This was probably because for many papers, their city names were spelled differently. Also, several Ukrainian cities changed their names. For example, Krasnoarmeisk was previously known as Pokrovsk and as Grishino.

For the last two years, 2020-21, we downloaded the details of all WoS papers with an address in Ukraine for a more detailed analysis. They numbered 23,794 in total. We were interested to learn about the funding bodies who had supported this research, and their names are given in the WoS in two searchable fields, the “funding organization” and the “full funding text”. The former separates the individual funders with semi-colons, so that they can easily be counted (although some are given twice or more). The latter allows acknowledgements which are in fact statements of conflict of interest (CoI), mostly to pharmaceutical companies, to be identified (see Lewison & Sullivan, 2015) and the funding data to be ignored if the financial support was not for the research described in the current paper. We determined the mean numbers of funding acknowledgements for papers in each major field, and also looked at which sectors were providing support (international, governmental, private-non-profit, commercial).

Since 2009, the WoS has also been tagging individual authors with their addresses, so we were able to list the names of the authors in the 26 individual *oblasts*, primarily from the names of cities if the name of the *oblast* was not specified in the address. For each *oblast*, we listed the surnames and the given names of the researchers, and hence their “abbreviated names” consisting of their surname and first initial. This enabled us to identify the different individuals, although occasionally they may have been duplicated if their surnames were transcribed differently into the Roman alphabet, or omitted if two researchers had the same surname and initial. [The listing was reverse alphabetically, so that we retained the researchers’ given names if some of their papers only had an initial and not a given name.]

We listed all the surnames of the Ukrainian researchers, and also those of Russian researchers in recent years, and identified those where a name was at least ten times as common in one country as the other, with account taken of Russia having about six times as many papers as Ukraine. We were able to do the same for the given names of the two sets of researchers. We also used the website, www.forebears.io, to list the 1000 most common surnames and 1000 most common given names in the two countries, and added surnames and given names that

were similarly distinct to the lists of researcher names. Finally, we noted that only Ukrainians had surnames ending in *chuk*, *iuk* or *skyi*, and only Russians had surnames ending in *in* (e.g., Lenin, Putin, Stalin). These lists of names with definite heritage enabled us to mark many of the names of the researchers in each *oblast* as either Russian (RU) or Ukrainian (UA). For a few researchers, their surnames and given names were of different heritage; they were marked as being of unknown heritage.

As a separate exercise, we attempted to determine the sex of the Ukrainian researchers. We did this by reference to a large thesaurus of over 68,000 given names that had been sexed from a variety of sources (see Lewison et al., 2022). Names were only sexed if at least 75% of occurrences were of one sex. [This percentage is a compromise between our desire to make the sexing accurate, and the need to sex as many names as possible.] We added to this thesaurus with data on the sex of more given names from www.forebears.io and, for those researchers with only initials, not given names, their sex from their surnames if they had gendered endings: *ev*, *ov*, *skyi* for males, and *eva*, *ova*, *ska* for females. It was also possible to sex some researchers whose papers had both given names and just initials if they could be matched.

In order to see if either the heritage or sex of researchers had changed, perhaps as a result of the change of Ukrainian government, and the Russian take-over of Crimea, in 2014, we repeated the analyses for 2010-12 for a few *oblasts* where we thought it likely that there would be noticeable changes. These were Crimea, Donetsk, Luhansk, Poltava, and Ternopil.

These analyses were all based on the names of individual researchers. We carried out one further analysis in order to determine the overall contribution to research by males and females in each *oblast* in terms of the numbers of papers times the numbers of male or female authors. For example, a paper with six Ukrainian authors of whom two were male, three female, and one of unknown sex, would add two to the male tally and three to the female tally. This would allow us to calculate the average contribution of males and females in each *oblast*. We also compared the female presence in Ukrainian research with the percentage of authors who were of Ukrainian heritage.

Results

Over the last 27 years, Ukrainian scientific output has increased largely proportionately with world output, but with some changes that appeared to correlate with its political situation, see Figure 2. International collaboration appears to correlate almost inversely with output, so that periods of greater relative output have been ones of reduced percentage collaboration.

Ukrainian relative research output steadily decreased from the 1990s to 2014 from 0.5% down to 0.35%, and then it increased quite rapidly, following the change in government. However, the amount of international collaboration increased (as it did world-wide) up to 2014, and then sharply declined. The actual volume of international papers did not decline; there was just a large increase in Ukrainian domestic papers, whose volume had been going down from 2011 to 2014, and then more than doubled in 2015. This was partly because the WoS expanded its coverage of papers published in non-traditional countries in order to be more inclusive. In 2020-21, there were 6538 papers (27% of the total) published in 68 Ukrainian journals, and 416 papers (1.7%) in 153 Russian journals, indicating a movement towards the support of national journals in Ukraine. There was a change in the language of publication, too. In 2010-11, 9.1% of Ukrainian papers in the WoS were in Russian and only 3.3% in Ukrainian, but by 2020-21, the Russian-language papers had declined to 3.8% of the total, and Ukrainian-language ones had increased to 5.3%.

Between 2010-14 and 2017-21, there was a big increase in the size of the research teams on Ukrainian papers, according to data from *InCites*. The largest collaborations, with 100 or more authors, increased from 3% of papers to 5.8%, and modest ones, with between six and ten authors, went from 5% to almost 26%. Meanwhile, single-author papers declined from nearly 15% to just over 8% of the total.

Figure 2. Ukrainian research output, percentage of the world (squares, right scale) and percentage of internationally co-authored papers (triangles, left scale), 1995-2021; three-year moving averages.

For most of this study period, the group of countries with which Ukrainian researchers co-authored most papers was Western Europe, and the amount of collaboration steadily increased, reaching a peak in 2013 when over one quarter of all Ukrainian output was so co-authored. It then declined sharply, and in the last two years has been overtaken by papers co-authored with one or more EU Member States in Eastern Europe, particularly Poland. European collaboration has been much more extensive than with North America, probably because of geographical proximity, and a common heritage between Ukrainians in the west of the country and neighbouring EU Member States, see Figure 3.

Figure 3. Percentages of Ukrainian research papers co-authored with scientists from five other country groups, 1995-2021; three-year moving averages. For composition of these groups, see Table 2.

The sharp and continued relative decline of co-authorship with Canada and the USA since 2014 is perhaps surprising in view of the political and military support that they have given to Ukraine. However, the actual number of joint papers increased, and was half as great again in 2021 compared with 2012 (928 compared with 614).

Figure 4. Percentage of Ukrainian research papers in 2020-21 that were internationally co-authored, by major scientific field. For field codes, see caption to Figure 1.

The amount of international collaboration varied considerably by scientific field, see Figure 4. Chemistry was the most collaborative field in 2020-21 with 35% of its papers co-authored internationally, and humanities the least, with less than 5%. The different groups of countries also varied in their contributions to Ukrainian research outputs, see Figure 5.

Figure 5. The contributions of different country groups to Ukrainian research in 2020-21 in different scientific fields. For composition of these groups, see Table 2. Fields ordered in descending order of outputs. For field codes, see caption to Figure 1.

Western Europe contributed most in medicine (MEDI) and mathematics (MATH); Eastern Europe in engineering (ENGR) and agriculture (AGRI); the Former Soviet Union countries in humanities (HUMA); Asian countries in agriculture (perhaps surprisingly) and materials science (MATE); Canada and the USA in information science (INFO; data not shown); and the rest of the world in physics (PHYS).

The mean five-year citation scores for Ukraine and its seven neighbours in 2013-17 are shown as a chart in Figure 6. It is striking that the impact of Ukrainian papers is so modest, being only slightly greater than that of Russian papers, and barely half that of Hungary. Although four of its neighbours are European Union Member States, two (Belarus and Moldova) are not, and their scientific outputs are much smaller than that of Ukraine. However, their superior citation scores are largely attributable to their high percentages of internationally collaborative papers (65% and 63%, respectively, compared with 40% for Ukraine). Their purely domestic papers are far less cited than their international ones: 2.3 and 1.9 citations in five years, compared with 2.5 for Ukraine. On the other hand, Slovakia, with 54% of its papers internationally co-authored, achieved a citation score of $ACI = 5.5$ for its domestic papers, more than twice that of Ukraine.

Figure 6. Mean five-year citation scores (ACI) for all research papers in 2013-17 from Ukraine and its seven neighbouring countries.

The percentage of reviews is a simple measure of the esteem of the leading scientists in an area, and it is everywhere in Ukraine well below the world average over the period of 6.1%. This suggests that, although Ukrainian total research output was more than commensurate with its GDP, its researchers were not particularly well regarded externally.

The amount of funding for Ukrainian research in the various major fields varied greatly, from an average of 9.4 funders per paper in physics to 0.05 in humanities. However, the former figure was greatly inflated by the 336 papers published from CERN (the European Organization for Nuclear Research in Geneva, of which Ukraine is an Associate Member), which averaged an astonishing 74 funders per paper. Figure 7 shows the average number of funders per paper for the different fields; they are ordered in descending order of output. Almost all the funding appeared to be from governmental sources, not the private sector. Of these, Ukraine unsurprisingly provided by far the most with 3225 papers acknowledging its support, but this represented only 11% of the total. The next highest source of support was the European Union, with 1167 (4.1%), followed by Russia (840, 3.0 %) and Germany (749, 2.6%). Overall, only 27% of these Ukrainian research papers had a financial acknowledgement, and only 0.17% reported a potential CoI, which reflects the small amount of medical research.

Figure 7. Average number of funders acknowledged on Ukrainian research papers, 2020-21, in different major fields. Note: physics papers from CERN have been removed.

The outputs of the 26 *oblasts* are shown in Table 3, and Figure 8 shows the ratios of the output of Ukraine, and the eight leading *oblasts*, to the world over the 27-year study period, as three-year moving averages. Ukraine is shown as a percentage, and the individual *oblasts* as per thousand values.

There is a substantial variation with time between the different *oblasts*. Figure 8 shows that the output from the capital, Kyiv, has grown very rapidly, and especially since 2014 and the Russian invasion of Donetsk and Luhansk, and the take-over of Crimea. There has been a nearly continuous decline in the output of Donetsk and Crimea since 1998, but not that of Luhansk, which was always tiny, but slightly increased from 2003 to 2021. Several *oblasts* have shown an increase of output relative to the world since 2014, notably Kharkiv (KHA), Lviv (LVV), Dnipropetrovsk (DNI) and Odesa (ODE), very likely because of the re-location of several research institutes in Donetsk and Crimea. For example, Donetsk National University moved to Vinnytsia, and the Institute of Applied Mathematics and Mechanics of the Ukrainian National Academy of Sciences moved to Sloviansk. Sumy has also progressed in the last eight years.

We turn now to the composition of the Ukrainian research workforce in 2020-21. Figure 9 shows the different *oblasts* of Ukraine with the percentages of researchers with names indicative of Russian heritage (relative to the total with either Russian or Ukrainian heritage). The percentage is much the highest in Crimea (not shown), and it was almost as high (81%) in 2010-12, showing that it was not the Russian invasion of 2014 that caused this. There is a clear gradient from west to east, corresponding to Ukraine's history. In the Donbas region, *oblasts* Donetsk and Luhansk, the percentages of researchers with Russian heritage declined markedly from 2010-12 to 2020-21. It went down from 61% to 50% in Donetsk and from 64% to 38% in Luhansk. It also declined in Poltava, from 39% to 21%, but not in Ternopil, where the Russian heritage percentage remained at just 16%.

Table 3. Outputs of WoS papers (articles and reviews) from the 26 individual Ukrainian *oblasts*, 1995-2021; the number of reviews (Revs), percentage of reviews (% R), and the ratio of outputs in 2017-21 to those in 1995-99. See caveat on the figures, above.

<i>Oblast</i>	<i>Papers</i>	<i>Revs</i>	<i>% R</i>	<i>Ratio</i>	<i>Oblast</i>	<i>Papers</i>	<i>Revs</i>	<i>% R</i>	<i>Ratio</i>
Ukraine	147907	2920	1.97	3.0	Zaporizhzhia	1858	71	3.82	90
Kyiv city	70275	1548	2.20	2.8	Poltava	1538	53	3.45	24
Kharkiv	28867	448	1.55	3.0	Kyiv region	1507	24	1.59	26
Lviv	10821	193	1.78	7.5	Ternopil	1377	41	2.98	69
Donetsk	7144	114	1.60	1.7	Cherkasy	1288	12	0.93	21
Dnipropetrovsk	7136	106	1.49	4.3	Vinnytsia	1239	23	1.86	58
Odesa	6954	116	1.67	4.0	Kherson	929	15	1.61	19
Crimea	3687	73	1.98	0.9	Rivne	833	10	1.20	30
Chernihiv	3305	27	0.82	5.1	Zhytomyr	828	5	0.60	128
Sumy	3027	84	2.78	11	Mykolaiv	501	1	0.20	
Chernivtsi	2587	24	0.93	4.0	Luhansk	433	3	0.69	17
Khmelnyskyi	1976	33	1.67	33	Kirovohrad	351	3	0.85	14
Ivano-Frankivsk	1961	81	4.13	52	Zakarpattia	266	0	0.00	93
Volyn	1917	16	0.83	23	Total	162605	3124	1.92	3.9

Figure 8. The variation of the research output of Ukraine, percentage of the world, and of eight leading *oblasts*, parts per thousand, from 1995 to 2021, three-year running means. *Oblast* codes: CNV = Chernihiv; CRI = Crimea; DNI = Dnipropetrovsk; DON = Donetsk; KHA = Kharkiv; KYV = Kyiv; LVV = Lviv; ODE = Odesa.

Figure 9. Map of Ukraine showing the percentages of researchers in each *oblast* in 2020-21 with names of either Ukrainian or Russian heritage that were Russian. *Note: Crimea not shown as part of Ukraine; the percentage of names of Russian heritage was 82.6%.*

Figure 10. Scatter plot of the percentage of Ukrainian researchers in 2020-21 who are female (ordinate) as a function of the percentage of researchers with either Russian or Ukrainian heritage who can be identified as Russian in each *oblast*, and in Ukraine as a whole (UA). *For trigraph oblast codes, see Table 1.*

The percentage of female researchers was remarkably high all over Ukraine, averaging 54%. It was highest in Volyn, in the far west, at almost 69%, and lowest in Crimea, at 44%. We noticed that it appeared to be *inversely* correlated with the percentage of researchers with names of Russian heritage, see Figure 10.

Our last analysis was of the contributions to Ukrainian research by males and females. We counted the total numbers of papers by all males and females, including those made by duplicate names. Overall, women contributed to 1.83 papers in the two years, and men to 2.42 papers, one third more. However, in four *oblasts*, women published more than men (Khernolnytskyi, the Kyiv region, Vinnytsia, and Rivne) by a modest amount.

Discussion

Ukraine, despite its relative lack of wealth, has published many research papers throughout the 27 years of our study period. This has probably been helped by its close association with the European Union Member States, both those from Western and from Eastern Europe. However, its research portfolio was rather unbalanced (see Figure 1), and Ukraine published much more research, especially in physics, than would have been expected. There was remarkably little contestable funding, and that was almost all from governmental sources. The exception was the 4% of papers that received support from the European Union, and a competition for 2020 announced by the (Ukrainian) National Research Foundation (<https://nrfu.org.ua/en/news-en/national-research-fund-announce-first-competitions-for-scientists-next-spring/>). This lack of contestable funding may have been responsible for the paucity of reviews, which (since 2003) has been more marked in Ukrainian domestic (i.e., without international collaboration) papers (1.5%) than in ones with foreign partners (2.7%). Ukrainian research was also poorly cited, compared with that of its seven neighbouring countries, as Figure 6 shows clearly. In part, this was because Ukraine's research was less international than that of its neighbours, which again suggests that despite the volume of output its researchers were not highly esteemed as partners.

Geographically, research was heavily concentrated in the areas around the capital, Kyiv, and the other big cities, notably Kharkiv, but was relatively neglected in the *oblasts* now occupied by Russia, namely Crimea, Donetsk, and Luhansk. It was also declining in those areas relative to world output, whereas in the other *oblasts* it increased sharply after 2015, mainly because of the expansion of the WoS to include journals published in a wider range of countries. We also noted that relatively little attention was given to medical, biological and agricultural research. One consequence may have been a rather higher burden of disease (expressed in Disability-Adjusted Life Years, DALYs) *per caput* than its geographical neighbours, see Table 4. This has improved over the years, but not so much as in Russia, which was very unhealthy in 2000 and in the years following the break-up of the Soviet Union.

Table 4. The burden of disease in seven Eastern European countries, 2000 to 2019. Population in millions; DALYs in thousands. Ratio = rate in 2019 / rate in 2000.

Country	2000			2010			2019			Ratio
	Pop'n	DALYs	Rate	Pop'n	DALYs	Rate	Pop'n	DALYs	Rate	
Russia	146.4	80276	548	143.5	70554	492	145.9	59384	407	0.74
Belarus	9.9	4512	457	9.4	4337	460	9.5	3556	376	0.82
Ukraine	48.8	24738	507	45.8	21783	476	44.0	18640	424	0.84
Moldova	4.2	1779	423	4.1	1756	429	4.0	1464	362	0.86
Slovakia	5.4	1756	325	5.4	1741	322	5.5	1663	305	0.94

Romania	22.1	8587	388	20.5	7862	384	19.4	7345	379	0.98
Poland	38.6	12644	328	38.3	12471	325	37.9	12302	325	0.99

Our analysis has shown that onomastics (the study of the origins of names) can reveal some interesting data about a country's research, and in particular the heritage of its researchers and their sex. However, this may give incorrect results for individuals, although it is usually fairly accurate for large groups. It can show some time trends, and provide the basis for discussions on science policy in a country and whether it is achieving its objectives, particularly at a time of major political and social changes. For example, we have shown that government policy in South Africa (Lewison & Jacobs, 2011) and in Malaysia (Lewison et al., 2016) has been effective in the promotion of previously under-represented ethnic groups.

Ukraine has provided good opportunities for female researchers, and in some areas of the country they made up more than 60% of the total, which is very high by world standards. Their presence was higher where the percentage of Russian-heritage researchers was low, such as in the west of Ukraine, but female access to research careers may be more dependent on some other factors, such the availability of affordable child-care.

The impact of the ongoing conflict is likely to exacerbate the geographical inequalities around research activity. In the post-conflict period, Ukraine will experience very different patterns of research. For example, there may be a greater emphasis on the biomedical and health sciences as the country capitalises on its closer alignment with Europe, and in particular with the Horizon research funding programme. Other funding schemes to help Ukrainian science are being planned, such as a joint scheme between the US National Academy of Sciences and the Polish Academy of Sciences for 2023 (Stone, 2022), and support from some instrument and equipment manufacturers.

There is an important *caveat* that must be noted about some of the work described here. Because Ukrainian names and place-names are written in the Cyrillic alphabet, and there is no standard means of transcription to the Roman alphabet (as there is now, for example, for Chinese characters with Pinyin), many such words will have been transcribed differently on different papers. So the counts of authors may well be too high, and some names may have been transcribed in such a way that their characteristics are no longer typical of Russian or Ukrainian heritage. On the other hand, the geographical search for papers from the individual *oblasts* will have missed many papers with variant city name spellings, and it was almost impossible to list all of these in the filters that we developed. Consequently, the counts of these papers will be too low, and it may have affected some *oblasts* more than others. However, the temporal variation seen in Figure 8 may be less affected by this problem than the actual numbers shown in Table 3.

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